

A EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON FORMING RATE OF THE SURFACE FILM ON LIQUID ALUMINUM*

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SUMMARY: A new way to detect the breaking force and forming rate of the surface film on liquid aluminum alloy in air was test. The computer recorded the curves of breaking force to time. Test shown that the surface film on liquid aluminum at 745°C in air will take more than 1.2 second to form a new strength-film after the old one been broken.

KEYWORDS: test method, alumina film, aluminum matrix composite

INTRODUCTION

The metal matrix composite has relied largely on expensive squeeze casting. It is the cost of this process has kept MMC tied to the high-end of the component sector [1]. During casting a tough oxide layer forms, which prevents the free-flow of melted metal into the fiber preform. High pressure is essential in order to achieve a fully dense MMC part. If the infiltration process can finish before the oxide player forms, the infiltration will be easier. This paper is to find the forming rate of the layer on the liquid aluminium [2].

Most of the research work on the oxide layer is about its thermodynamics, and in dynamics it often thought that the oxide layer is formed at no time. This paper designed a device to test its break behavior, and found the curves of breaking force to time.

THE DEVICE TO TEST THE OXIDE LAYER

Fig 1. The device to test the oxide player on liquid aluminium

¹This device is mainly based on a material testing-machine as figure 1. A stainless steel bar connected to a special sensor can move with the beam of the material testing-machine. The

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beam can move at different rate repositively. The diameter of the bar is 3 mm. A crucible with electric stove is setting under the beam. When the bar move down and touched the surface of the liquid aluminum in the crucible the sensor can detect the reaction force by the stainless steel bar. Following the move of the bar the force begin to increase. When the force increases enough to break the film the force will sharp fell down. But the broken film will mend quickly to form a new one. Along with the moving of the bar the force will increase again and a zigzag curve is formed as fig 2. The curves shape and peak value are different with the alloy content, test temperature and moving velocity of the bar.

Fig. 2 the typical zigzag curve for aluminum alloy at 700°C

At first a graphite bar was used as the stainless one, because it will react to the air at 700°C and the test results is out of orderliness, this graphite bar can be used at vacuume conditions late. The resolution of the special sensor is 0.5 mN.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This paper test the curve shape at different temperature and different moving velocity for ZL109, ZL102, LD2 aluminum alloy. All the curves are show a zigzag shape at low moving velocity. Alloy content is the main factor to the average breaking force. Among them the ZL102 is of the lowest average breaking force. Test at 800-900°C for LD2 alloy shown that the breaking force is decreased with the temperature raised because the fluidity of the liquid almunium is increased with the temperature.

The experiment tested aluminum alloy LD2 at 745°C at different moving velocity of the bar. The test results are show in figure 3 ,4 and 5. These figures show that the average peak value of the cures was decrease with the increase of the moving rate of the bar. At the rate of 8 mm/min the curve losted its zigzag forms. From figure 4 we can count that there are about 60 zigzag peaks. The average time between tow peaks is about 2.4 seconds at the rate of 4 mm/min. When the rate increase to 8 mm/min the time between tow peaks is less than 1.2 second. So it can be deduced that the oxide player can forms at no time but its strength will take a longer period to increase. More tests on casting aluminium alloy are also show that at the rate of 8 mm/min the curve will last its zigzag forms.

Fig. 3 The zigzag curve of the reaction force to the displacement of the bar at the rate of 2 mm/min

Fig. 4 The zigzag curve of the reaction force to the displacement of the bar at the rate of 4 mm/min

Fig. 5 The curve of the reaction force to the displacement of the bar at the rate of 8 mm/min

CONCLUSION

This device mainly based on a material testing-machine is an easy way to detect the machine breaking behavior of the liquid aluminum surface film. This test can also be used to detect the surface tension of other film. For ZL109, ZL102, LD2 aluminum alloy, all the curves are show a zigzag shape at low moving velocity. Among them the ZL102 is of the lowest average breaking force. Test at 800-900°C for LD2 alloy shown that the breaking force will decreased with the temperature raised. Test shown that the surface film on liquid LD2 aluminum alloy at 745°C in air will take more than 1.2 second to form a new strength-film after the old one been broken. We can deduced that for the squeeze casting process the flow rate of the liquid aluminum must more than 8 mm/min or more. When this rate been achieved the influence of

surface film can be minimize.

REFERENCE

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